

The formation of Schiff's bases of 1:2 type (aldehyde: carbazide) is indicated from analysis. The presence of an aromatic type structure is recognised⁴ by the presence of =C-H stretching vibrations near 3030 cm^{-1} and C=C vibrations in the region, 1590 to 1500 cm^{-1} . The absorption bands observed near 3440 to 3340 cm^{-1} and 1645 cm^{-1} correspond to N-H stretching and NH_2 deformation, respectively. The strong absorption peak at 1660 cm^{-1} in the spectra of (I) is due to the presence of C=O group and C=S group in (II) is indicated by the peak at 1495 cm^{-1} . The C=N linkage of Schiff's base type⁴ is confirmed by the bands near 2330 cm^{-1} in both the compounds. A very sharp absorption band at 1340 cm^{-1} in the spectra of compound (II) shows the C-N stretching of Ar-N type. The C=N-N and N-C-N type linkages are shown by peaks near 1510 cm^{-1} and 1440 cm^{-1} .⁵

The purity of the compounds were checked by TLC.

Experimental

Materials: Samples of terephthalaldehyde (Koch-Light); semicarbazide hydrochloride and 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide (Fluka), were employed. Solvents used were of reagent grade.

Preparation of terephthalaldehyde bis-(semicarbazone) (TPBS): Semicarbazide hydrochloride, 11.15 g, 0.1 mole was dissolved in 100 ml hot water and 50 ml 1N NaOH solution was added. This solution was mixed with terephthalaldehyde (6.70 g, 0.05 mole dissolved in 100 ml ethanol) gradually with constant stirring. On shaking for a few minutes, a yellow coloured powdery solid separated. The whole mass was then refluxed over a waterbath for 1hr to ensure the completion of the reaction and the solid was filtered, washed with hot water, ethanol, and ether successively, and dried under reduced pressure over calcium chloride; yield 86%. Found: C, 48.06; H, 4.53; N, 32.94; Calc. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N}_6$; C, 48.32; H, 4.83; N, 33.57%.

The compound is insoluble in water, acetone, ethanol, chloroform, benzene, tetrahydrofuran, but has a little solubility in dimethylformamide and dimethylsulphoxide.

Preparation of terephthalaldehyde bis-(4-phenylthiosemicarbazone), (TPBPTS): 8.35g, 0.05 mole 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide dissolved in 150ml ethanol was added to an ethanolic solution of terephthalaldehyde (3.35g, 0.025 mole dissolved in 50ml ethanol) and the mixture was refluxed over a waterbath for ca 2h. A yellow solid separated, which was left for few hours and filtered, washed with ethanol and ether, and dried under reduced pressure over calcium chloride; yield 84%.

The compound is insoluble in water and other common organic solvents, but highly soluble in dimethylformamide and dimethylsulphoxide. Found: C, 60.67; H, 5.06; N, 19.50; Calc. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_6\text{S}_2$; C, 61.10; H, 4.66; N, 19.44%.

Infra-red absorption spectra: The i.r. absorption spectra were recorded with a Beckmann infra-red spectrophotometer in the range of 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} using KBr pellets.

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Unsaponifiable Matter of *Cordia rothii* Roem & Schult (Fruits)

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CORDIA rothii Roem & Schult^{1,2,3} (N. O. Boraginaceae, Hindi-Gondi) has fruits of sweetish mucilaginous taste, aromatic agreeable odour and good source of carbohydrates.

Due to its nutritive value it was taken up for phytochemical investigations. The present communication describes the study of the unsaponifiable matter from the fruits.

4 kg. powdered fruits on extraction with petroleum ether (40-60°) in a soxhlet extractor and removal of the solvent under reduced pressure yielded 75 g. of a yellow coloured fatty material. On saponification with 0.5 N KOH it yielded an unsaponifiable matter which was extracted with ether. Removal of ether gave a waxy residue (3.10 g.) which was subjected to column chromatography over 125 g. of alumina. The column was successively eluted with (i) petroleum ether (60-80°), (ii) petroleum ether (60-80°) : benzene (2:1) and (iii) benzene : chloroform (1:1). The three eluates were collected separately and solvent distilled off under reduced pressure. The residue from the eluates (i) on

crystallisation from acetone gave shining crystalline plates (m. p. 64°). The compound gave negative tests of all classes of compounds. Its stability, negative reactions with bromine water and KMnO_4 suggested its saturated nature. It was identified as *n*-hentriacontane by mixed m.p. and co-chromatography with authentic sample. IR and NMR data further confirm its identity as *n*-hentriacontane.

The residue from eluates (ii) on crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and methanol (1:1) yielded white flakes m.p. 199°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 87^\circ$ (CHCl_3), its acetate, m.p. 237°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 80^\circ$ (CHCl_3). It gave positive Liebermann-Burchard reaction and Nollers' reaction for triterpene. Mixed m.p. determination and co-chromatography with authentic sample confirmed it as β -amyrin.

The residue from eluates (iii) yielded another colourless compound, crystallising from methanol:ethylacetate (1:1), m.p. 136–7°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 31^\circ.0$ (CHCl_3). It gave positive Salkowski and Liebermann-Burchard reactions for sterol and was identified as β -sitosterol by mixed m.p. and co-chromatography with authentic sample.

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Synthesis of Pyrazolyl Schiff Bases

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SCHIFF bases have gained prominence as pharmacologically important substances. They have anticancer or antituberculostatic activity¹. Anticancer schiff bases² have been prepared by the condensation of aniline with substituted benzaldehydes. Pyrimidine schiff bases^{3,4} were synthesised as possible anticancer agents. A careful literature survey revealed that no such schiff bases have been investigated in the pyrazolone series. In view of the marked pharmacological importance of this class of compound we thought it would be of interest to investigate the schiff bases having a pyrazolone nucleus. 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one on fusion with acetamide followed by alkaline hydrolysis and subsequent acidification yields the 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-acetyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one. Ethanolic solution of the methyl ketone when heated with

aniline affords the schiff base. The formation of the schiff base has been confirmed by a single step synthesis involving the fusion of 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one with acetanilide at 200–20° for 6 hr. The identity of the two products obtained by the two different methods was established from the analytical values and mixed m.p. The I. R. absorption spectra of the two products were superimposable.

In the present communication 24 schiff bases were prepared using *o*-, *m*-, *p*-substituted aniline, benzidine, *m*-phenylene diamine, glycine, sulphadiazine and sulphaguanidine. In the case of *o*-nitro aniline no condensation product was obtained even though the reaction was carried out for 12 hr. in the presence of fused sodium acetate. Failure of the *o*-nitro aniline to undergo condensation is possibly due to the extremely weak basicity and steric hindrance. The formation of schiff bases have been proved from the following observations: (i) Failure to react with characteristic carbonyl reagents and therefore indicating that the ketonic group present in acetyl pyrazolone must have reacted with the amino groups of the compounds under reference, (ii) Positive test with ethanolic ferric chloride solution indicating the presence of a free $\geq\text{C}-\text{OH}$ group (keto-enol tautomeric form of >C=O at position 5).

Experimental

1. *Synthesis of 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-acetyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one*: It was prepared as per our earlier method⁵. m. p. 58°, yield 60%.

It was soluble in aq. sodium hydroxide and gave colouration with ethanolic ferric chloride solution.

2. *Synthesis of schiff base*: 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-acetyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (0.01 mole and in the case of diamine 0.02 mole), aniline (0.01 mole), ethanol (20 ml) were heated on a water bath for 4 hr. On cooling the product that separated was filtered. Crystallisation from ethanol yields the shining pale yellow crystalline schiff base from aniline, m. p. 189°, yield 60% (Found: C, 74.11; H, 5.54; N, 41.21% $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{O}$ requires; C, 74.22; H, 5.84; N, 41.43%).

Condensation with the substituted aniline, amino acid, diamine, benzthiazole sulphadiazine and sulphaguanidine were carried out exactly by the above procedure. The m. p. and analytical values are given in Table 1.

3. *Synthesis of schiff base (one step synthesis)*: An intimate mixture of finely powdered 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one (3 g.) and acetanilide (3 g.) was heated to 200–20° in an oil-bath for 6 hr. The dark coloured liquid was allowed to cool overnight. It was then treated with ethanol and allowed to stand for 96 hr. The solid thus obtained was filtered and washed with hot water to remove unaltered 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one and acetanilide and finally